

RECENT RESULTS FROM THE InP HOMOJUNCTION CELL MODULE
ON THE LIPS III SPACECRAFT

David J. Brinker and Irving Weinberg
NASA Lewis Research Center
Cleveland, Ohio 44135

ABSTRACT

The flight performance of the Lewis Research Center' indium phosphide homojunction cell module on the LIPS III spacecraft is presented. Four n⁺p diffused junction cells, an early product of an InP development program, were flown. The voltage range of the data prohibits determination of the open-circuit voltage or the maximum power point. However, analysis of the 32 months of short-circuit current data reveals a slight increase, not the 4% decrease expected from radiation tolerance studies. This increase may be due to continual cleaning of possible prelaunch dust contamination or changes in data acquisition system calibration. For all cells, the average short-circuit current remains below prelaunch values.

INTRODUCTION

The NASA Lewis Research Center placed a module of indium phosphide homojunction solar cells on the third Living Plume Shield (LIPS III) spacecraft. The cells were an early product of a development program which has the goal of maximizing end-of-life performance of InP solar cells through the optimization of conversion efficiency and radiation tolerance. However, a synergistic simulation of the many components of the low earth orbit space environment is not possible. Hence, actual flight testing of new technologies is necessary. The first opportunity to test InP solar cells occurred in the Summer of 1986 with the announcement of LIPS III by the Naval Research Laboratory. Although InP cells were limited in efficiency and size at that time, space solar cell flight experiments are rare occurrences and the decision was made to test available InP cells. The spacecraft was launched in the late Spring of 1987 and continues to successfully telemeter data from solar cells of numerous materials and designs. In this paper we report on the continued performance of the InP homojunction solar cells on the LIPS III spacecraft.

FLIGHT MODULE DESCRIPTION

The InP homojunction solar cells flown on this experiment were fabricated by Rensselaer Polytechnic Institute using the open tube diffusion of sulfur into p-type InP substrates (1). A cell area of 0.313 cm² was delineated on the wafer by mesa etching. Figure 1 illustrates the details of the cell structure. Cell efficiencies, ranging from 11.36 to 14.31 percent (Air Mass Zero, 25 °C) for the lot of 15 cells fabricated for this experiment, were measured in our laboratory prior to module fabrication.

Two flight modules of four cells each, a prime and a reserve, were fabricated. Module construction was performed by Spectrolab, Inc. under contract to the Lewis Research Center. The module, shown in Figure 2, was built on a 5 centimeters square, 1.6 millimeter thick aluminum substrate. The module contains four cells, each covered with a 12 mil fused silica microsheet. Each cell is connected to the data system with a four-wire harness, with redundant positive and negative leads provided. In this manner, current-voltage characteristics can be measured for each cell independently. A fifth, centrally located cell covers a ceramic-based platinum resistance thermal detector. Further details of the module design and fabrication have been previously published (2).

InP HOMOJUNCTION CELL CHARACTERIZATION

As part of the development program, an extensive set of laboratory tests were conducted on InP cells, including those made by open tube diffusion. The results of these tests have allowed for prediction of flight test results and for normalization of the flight data with respect to operating temperature. The temperature dependency of the major solar cell parameters had been previously measured (3) for InP cells of this design and fabrication technology. Since the nature of the flight data returned from LIPS III for this experiment prohibits accurate determination of

anything but the short-circuit current, its temperature dependency is the the only parameter of interest. For open-tube diffused InP cells, the variation in short-circuit current with temperature was determined, using a Spectrolab X-25L solar simulator, to be $+0.0223 \text{ mA/cm}^2\text{-K}$.

Since one of the objectives of the experiment is to measure the degree of performance degradation in the natural radiation environment of the LIPS spacecraft orbit, the dependency of short-circuit current with irradiation was needed. As a consequence of early research which showed indium phosphide superior to both silicon and gallium arsenide in a laboratory radiation environment, extensive radiation tolerance studies were conducted (3). The dependency of short-circuit current with 1 MeV electrons is shown in Figure 3. Due to the immaturity of indium phosphide as a space cell material and the as yet lack of standardization of cell type and configuration, damage equivalents do not exist for it. Therefore, silicon equivalent fluences were used for analysis purposes; $6.49 \times 10^{11}/\text{yr}$ equivalent 1 MeV electrons/cm² for electrons and $2.28 \times 10^{13}/\text{yr}$ equivalent 1 MeV electrons for protons (4). An effect unique to InP may also play a role in understanding the flight data. It has been demonstrated that if InP cells are illuminated while undergoing irradiation, the performance degradation is significantly reduced (5). Based on the data from Figure 3 and this effect, one would expect to see very little degradation in short-circuit current during the initial few years on-orbit.

The current-voltage characteristics of the completed flight module was measured in our solar simulator after fabrication. This data, Table 1, was used as a reference point for analysis of the flight data.

FLIGHT RESULTS

The LIPS III spacecraft, in a circular orbit of 1100 kilometers altitude and 60+° inclination, has been aloft for about three years. Data has been received from the first 971 days on-orbit, amounting to 12,989 revolutions. Cell temperature ranged from a low of -21 °C to a high of 39 °C, with the majority of the reading greater than 20 °C. The variation in temperature is likely a function of the time interval between the end of the eclipse period and acquisition of the data. The voltage range of the I-V data received for all cells is not sufficient to include the open-circuit voltage, nor can it be reliably calculated from the data. Therefore, only the short-circuit current will be discussed.

Figures 4 through 7 show the short-circuit current of the four InP cells as a function of time-on-orbit. The data has been normalized to

25 °C and to one AMO sun (earth-sun distance = 1.00 AU). Initial on-orbit currents are 3.7 to 6.2 percent less than the pre-flight simulator data. Several factors can contribute to this. At the time of module fabrication, InP primary calibration standards did not exist so a GaAs standard was used. Also, an accumulation of dust prior to launch has been reported by the spacecraft designers (6). Sufficient dust could lead to light attenuation on the order of this initial decrease. A final cause could be a difference in the calibration of the laboratory solar simulator data system and the spacecraft data acquisition system. The initial drop is likely to be a combination of these possibilities.

The scatter in the data for each cell is at most 4%, which compares favorably with the maximum expected error of 5% in the current measurement system (7). A mechanism to account for I_{sc} values which are significantly higher in value than the average has been proposed by the spacecraft designers (7). A study of the first 130 days of data concluded that there is good correlation between solar reflectance from the Earth (such as the Pacific Ocean) and an increase in the I_{sc} data of a number of experiments. Tracking station operations have been modified to reduce or eliminate this effect.

The general trend of the short-circuit current data is upward, with an increase of about 3 percent over the 32 month span of the flight data. From the laboratory radiation resistance studies, a decrease of about 4% is expected. If the effect of irradiation while under illumination is considered, a negligible decrease in I_{sc} is expected. We know of no data which indicates improvement of InP cell performance, over preirradiation values, when irradiation is conducted in the presence of light.

If the cells were indeed covered with dust during prelaunch operations, and continual cleaning has been occurring, then an increase in I_{sc} is understandable. A change in calibration of the data acquisition system would also explain the data. It should be noted that in all cases, the average short-circuit current remains at levels below the pre-launch values. Additional flight data and comparison with other experiments on LIPS III may yield the answer.

CONCLUSIONS

Flight data from the first 971 days on-orbit of the Lewis Research Center's module of four InP homojunction solar cells has been received. The voltage range of the data prohibits determination of the open-circuit voltage or the maximum power point. The expected slight decrease in short-circuit current due to the natural radiation flux has not been seen,

in fact the trend in I_{sc} is slightly upward. This increase may be due to continual cleaning of possible prelaunch dust contamination or changes in data acquisition system calibration. For all cells, the average short-circuit current remains below prelaunch values.

REFERENCES

1. K.K. Parat, S. Bothra, J.M. Borrego and S.K. Gandhi, "Solar Cells in Bulk InP, Made by an Open Tube Diffusion Process," Solid State Electron., vol. 30 p.283, 1987
2. D.J. Brinker, R.E. Hart, Jr., I. Weinberg and B.S. Smith, "InP Homojunction Solar Cell Performance on the LIPS III Flight Experiment," Proc. Photovoltaic Specialists Conference, IEEE, p. 819, 1988.
3. I. Weinberg, C.K. Swartz, R.E. Hart, Jr., S.K. Gandhi, J.M. Borrego, K.K. Parat and M. Yamaguchi, "Comparative Radiation Resistance, Temperature Dependence and Performance of Diffused Junction Solar Cells," Solar Cells, vol. 22, p. 113, 1987.
4. H.Y. Tada, J.R. Carter, B.E. Anspaugh and R.G. Downing, "Solar Cell Radiation Handbook, JPL Publication 82-69, 1982.
5. K. Ando and M. Yamaguchi, "Radiation Resistance in InP Solar Cells under Light Illumination," Appl. Phys. Lett., vol. 47, p. 846, 1985.
6. J.G. Severns, R.M. Hobbs, N.P Elliot, R.W. Towsley and G.F. Virshup, "The Experiments of LIPS III," Proc. Space Photovoltaic Research and Technology Conference, NASA CP-3030, p. 306, 1988.
7. J.G. Severns, R.W. Conway, B.J. Faraday and R.M. Hobbs, "Flight Experience with LIPS-III," Proc. 24th Intersociety Energy Conversion Engineering Conference, IEEE, p. 399, 1989.

Table 1 - AM0, 25 C I-V parameters of flight module in solar simulator

Cell number	V_{oc} , V	I_{sc} , mA	FF, percent	EFF, percent
1	0.800	7.86	78.2	11.45
2	.802	7.47	78.3	10.91
3	.805	7.63	80.2	11.47
4	.800	7.83	78.4	11.44
Average	0.802	7.70	78.8	11.32

Figure 1 - N⁺P InP cell structure

Figure 2 - InP flight module

Figure 3 - Normalized short-circuit current vs. 1 MeV electron fluence

Figure 4 - I_{sc} vs. time-on-orbit for cell 1 (Temp. and intensity corrected)

Figure 5 - I_{sc} vs. time-on-orbit for cell 2

Figure 6 - I_{sc} vs. time-on-orbit for cell 3

Figure 7- I_{sc} vs. time-on-orbit for cell 4